

The innermost regions of Young Stellar Objects as seen by VLTI/GRAVITY

K. Perraut¹, L. Labadie², L. Klarmann³, J. Bouvier¹, B. Tessore¹, G. Pantolmos¹, E. Alécian¹, M. Benisty^{1,4},
W. Brandner³, A. Caratti o Garatti⁵, C. Dougados¹, R. Garcia-Lopez⁵, J. Sanchez-Bermudez⁶ and
GRAVITY Collaboration

¹ Univ. Grenoble Alpes, CNRS, IPAG, 38000 Grenoble, France

² I. Physikalisches Institut, Universität zu Köln, Zùlpicher Strasse 77, 50937, Köln, Germany

³ Max Planck Institute for Astronomy, Königstuhl 17, 69117 Heidelberg, Germany

⁴ Unidad Mixta Internacional Franco-Chilena de Astronomía (CNRS UMI 3386), Departamento de Astronomía, Universidad de Chile, Camino El Observatorio 1515, Las Condes, Santiago, Chile

⁵ Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies, 31 Fitzwilliam Place, D02 XF86 Dublin, Ireland

⁶ Instituto de Astronomía, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Apdo. Postal 70264, Ciudad de México 04510, Mexico

Abstract

Understanding how the protoplanetary disks around young stars are structured and evolve is crucial for star and planet formation theories. We observed in an homogeneous way several tens of Herbig Ae/Be and T Tauri disks with the VLTI/GRAVITY instrument in the near-infrared K-band. We aim at spatially resolving the sub astronomical unit region to gain a statistical understanding of their morphological and compositional properties, and at looking for correlations with stellar parameters, such as luminosity, mass, and age. Thanks to its spectral resolution coupled with high angular resolution, VLTI/GRAVITY allows us to probe the location of the warm and hot gas in the inner disk. In a near future, the GRAVITY+ instrument will have a drastically improved sensitivity that will give us access to a much wider sample of young stars, including lower-mass stars and younger embedded targets.

1 Introduction

During their pre-main sequence phase, young stars are surrounded by protoplanetary disks that mostly consist of (hydrogen and helium) gas, with a small fraction of dust grains. These disks play a crucial role in star and planet formation as they are the reservoirs from which matter is accreted onto the star and planets are formed. To understand the diverse outcomes of planet formation, it is therefore crucial to understand the structure and evolution of protoplanetary disks, while planet formation occurs. ALMA images in the millimetric range and direct imaging in the optical have revealed the complexity and the diversity of the outer disks where spirals, arcs, and shadows have been observed (Long *et al.*, 2018; Garufi *et al.*, 2018). They may probe disk evolution, signposts of planets, and/or inner and outer disk misalignment.

In the innermost regions (i.e., at (sub-)astronomical unit scales), dust sublimates at the inner rim of the disks, dust traps and/or vortices can occur, and micron-sized dust grains can grow to pebbles and larger bodies producing the first building blocks of planets. Mass ejection through jets and winds, star-disk interactions, accretion shocks onto the star also impact the evolution of the central star itself and its disk. Constraining these innermost regions that might be as complex and dynamic as the outer ones is of utmost importance to understand stellar and planetary formation.

Since the advent of optical long-baseline interferometry, these innermost regions can be spatially resolved, at least

partially (see the pioneering works with Keck Interferometer: Akeson *et al.* (2005); Eisner *et al.* (2007, 2010) for instance). Thanks to the exquisite accuracy and sensitivity of the GRAVITY instrument installed at the combined focus of the VLTI (Gravity Collaboration *et al.*, 2017a), we are leading a Large Program of Young Stellar Objects (YSOs) in the near-infrared K-band with the aim of revisiting these pioneering works for homogeneous datasets. We take advantage of the coupling of high angular resolution and high spectral resolution to simultaneously study the dust emission and the hot and warm gas in the inner disk regions.

2 The GRAVITY YSO sample

Up to now, the GRAVITY YSO sample includes more than 40 Herbig stars, 20 less-massive, colder T Tauri stars, and 6 high-mass YSOs. With such a sample, we probe a large range in spectral type (from B2 to M0), luminosity ($0.4 - 10^4 L_{\odot}$), and age (0.04 to 14.5 Myr). Figure 1 shows our current sample in the Hertzsprung-Russell diagram. Our targets exhibit different disk properties with respect to Meeus' classification (Meeus *et al.*, 2001), including flaring (group I) and flat (group II) disks. Our sample also contains gapped and transitional disks. Since mid-infrared interferometry is a mean to probe the disk regions beyond the dust sublimation rim and thus to probe the disk flaring, we also selected stars that are part of the MIDI atlas (Menu *et al.*, 2015; Varga *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 1: The YSO GRAVITY sample plotted in the Hertzsprung-Russell diagram: Herbig Ae/Be stars (open circles) and T Tauri stars (colored circles). The different colors correspond to different star forming regions (Taurus: orange; Lupus: green; Ophiuchus: purple; and Corona Australis: blue; the others: black). Evolutionary tracks are used to derive masses and ages for both groups: the grey solid lines correspond to PISA iso-mass tracks (0.6 to $3 M_{\odot}$), and the dashed blue lines to PISA isochrones ($1, 2, 3, 5, 10, 12,$ and 100 Myr).

3 The properties of the inner dusty disks

GRAVITY observations were modeled with semi-physical geometrical models and the best fits provided us with the inner disk sizes and orientations. At our spatial resolution, the K-band continuum emitting regions appear as wide and smooth rings. The derived half-flux radii in the K-band can then be plotted as a function of the luminosity of the central star. The GRAVITY measurements extend this radius-luminosity relationship up to $\sim 10^4 L_{\odot}$ (Gravity Collaboration *et al.*, 2019), and confirm the significant spread around the mean trend $R \propto L^{1/2}$ (Figure 2). This correlation can be explained by the fact that the emission in the near-infrared is dominated by the dust located close to the dust sublimation radius, whose position itself is primarily constrained by the luminosity of the central star. The larger scatter at higher luminosities may be explained by gas shielding effects and/or active disks, while the putative over-estimate of the K-band size for the smaller luminosities is assumed to be due to the increasing contribution of stellar scattered light (Pinte *et al.*, 2008), which is not properly accounted for in our geometrical models (see insert of Figure 2).

Investigating the N-band to K-band size ratio as a function of mass and age for Herbig Ae/Be stars, we find that the low-luminosity, older sources exhibit a stronger scatter with values reaching above 100. In the mass range around $2 M_{\odot}$, we observe a correlation between the N-to-K size ratio and age, with objects transitioning from group II to group I. The

N-to-K size ratio thus appears as a proxy to disentangle the gapped and continuous disks (Gravity Collaboration *et al.*, 2019).

4 The location of the hot and warm gas

By coupling high angular resolution and spectral resolution up to 4000, GRAVITY allows us to spatially resolve the emitting regions of warm and hot gas in disks (Gravity Collaboration *et al.*, 2020a, 2021), to study the kinematics of ejection through jets and/or winds (Gravity Collaboration *et al.*, 2017b), and to probe the accretion flows onto the central star (Bouvier *et al.*, 2020b; Gravity Collaboration *et al.*, 2020b).

We spatially resolved for the first time the CO emitting region of NGC 2024 IRS (Gravity Collaboration *et al.*, 2020a). This well-studied high-mass YSO is very bright in the K-band and exhibits strong CO bandheads in emission. The GRAVITY interferometric observables provided a size measurement of the emitting regions of the K-band continuum and of the CO bandheads, respectively. Compared to the continuum K-band region, the CO emitting region is more compact. Both emitting regions have similar inclinations and position angles. The radial extent of the CO emitting region might be relatively small ($\leq 20\%$ of its radius) since we obtained the same results from the different bandheads that are excited at different temperatures. Using a CO model, the properties of the CO region can be deduced, such as the temperature and the column density. The derived temperature is higher than

Figure 2: The GRAVITY half-flux radii measured in the K-band for Herbig Ae/Be (grey symbols) and T Tauri (blue symbols) stars are plotted as a function of stellar luminosity. The colored lines correspond to a passively irradiated disk with an optically thin inner cavity for different dust cooling efficiencies ϵ (0.1: solid lines, and 1: dashed lines), and different temperatures for the dust grains (1300 K: blue, and 1700 K: orange). Adapted from Gravity Collaboration *et al.* (2019). The insert zooms on T Tauri stars and includes two models from Pinte *et al.* (2008) (solid grey and black lines) with different dust properties that correctly fit our measurements.

predicted for the disk mid-plane ($\sim 2,000$ K) and lower than what is expected for the disk surface ($\sim 4,500$ K). We therefore conclude that CO emission arises from an intermediate region. From the Doppler broadening of the bandheads, we derived the Keplerian velocity, and thus the mass of the central star. Assuming the star lies on the ZAMS, we deduce an effective temperature of 29,000 K, at which CO molecules should be photo-dissociated by the stellar UV photons. We conclude that the CO emitting-gas is shielded.

We used a similar approach to probe the accretion flows on T Tauri stars, e.g., on DoAr44, a solar-like young star with a transitional disk, whose compact inner disk accretes onto the central star and for which a misalignment between the inner and the outer disks is suspected due to the shadows observed in the disk outer ring (Casassus *et al.*, 2018). We recorded several hours of observations on this star across the Hydrogen I Br γ line with GRAVITY. Thanks to spectro-astrometry, we could probe the magnetosphere at a scale of a few stel-

lar radii. We detected a slight offset across the line with respect to the star, and confirmed the misalignments between the inner and outer disks (Bouvier *et al.*, 2020b). In addition to the GRAVITY observations, we recorded simultaneously photometry to have access to the variability, infrared spectra with CFHT/SPIRou over several stellar rotations, and visible spectro-polarimetric data with CFHT/ESPaDOnS to derive the topology of the magnetic field (Bouvier *et al.*, 2020a). All the observations are fully compatible with the magnetospheric accretion scenario. This is also the case for TW Hya whose GRAVITY observations led to an estimate of the size of the Br γ emitting region amounting to a few stellar radii, in excellent agreement with the magnetospheric size previously derived from the stellar magnetic field topology (Gravity Collaboration *et al.*, 2020b). Such multi-wavelength and multi-technique campaigns are crucial to understand the accretion process and the star-disk interactions in young solar-type stars.

Figure 3: Histogram of K-band magnitude for young stars observable with GRAVITY+ in the Taurus star forming region. Computed from the catalog of Galli *et al.* (2019).

5 The opportunity of GRAVITY+

The proposed upgrade of GRAVITY, called GRAVITY¹, will drastically increase the sensitivity and sky coverage, giving us access to the bulk of T Tauri stars. As an example, Figure 3 displays the histogram of K-band magnitudes for young stars that will be observable in the Taurus star forming region with GRAVITY+ when equipped with Laser Guide Stars. More than 230 targets have a K-band magnitude smaller than 10, which makes spectro-astrometry – as we did on DoAr44 and TW Hya – possible either on a representative T Tauri sample with a few hours of integration (as today with GRAVITY on stars with K-band magnitude of 7), or on brighter targets with shorter integration times, opening the opportunity to study the temporal variability of the accretion flows in these complex environments.

This improvement in sensitivity will permit to explore a larger parameter space, in terms of mass, age, and accretion rate. We will have access to different classes of YSOs, e.g. lower mass stars and younger embedded targets, and will probe different regimes of accretion to test whether the magnetospheric accretion scenario remains valid for stronger accretion rates, and for more intense and complex magnetic fields.

6 Conclusion and perspective

The K-band interferometric instrument GRAVITY installed at the VLTI has the capability of combining high angular resolution, reaching the sub-au scale for the closest star forming regions, and high spectral resolution. This allows us to investigate both the dusty and gaseous components of the inner regions of protoplanetary disks around young stars.

GRAVITY has enabled the first critical tests of the magnetospheric accretion scenario in young suns by probing the main accretion tracers through the HI Br γ line. GRAVITY+ will have the unique capability of routinely detecting such differential astrometric signals in selected accretion/ejection tracers with much improved significance.

A better understanding of the complex and variable inner-

most regions of circumstellar disks requires multi-technique and multi-wavelength campaigns. In parallel, advanced numerical modeling is required to interpret the huge amount of data and to optimize the observing strategies. Efforts in this direction are currently being developed, e.g., in the framework of the ERC SPIDI project², such as the non-LTE, multi-level atomic radiative transfer (RT) module developed by Tessore *et al.* (2021) and implemented in the MCFOST code (Pinte *et al.*, 2006, 2009). The RT code produces images of the star and of the accreting magnetosphere in spectral channels across emission line profiles, which can be converted into synthetic interferometric observables. Numerical magnetohydrodynamic models are also developed in order to compute the gas density and magnetic field structures in the inner regions of star-disk systems (see Haiku from G. Pantolmos in this conference or e.g., Pantolmos *et al.*, 2020). These observational campaigns and advanced numerical simulations are crucial to progress towards a comprehensive view of planet-forming disks, from their inner regions (< 0.1 au) to their outer parts.

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¹<https://www.mpe.mpg.de/ir/gravityplus>

²Web site: spidi-eu.org/

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